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ADVANTAGES, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS****Бринцева Олена,***Старший викладач кафедри ініомовної підготовки, європейської інтеграції та міжнародного співробітництва, Української Інженерно-Педагогічної Академії***Подорожна Аліна***Старший викладач кафедри ініомовної підготовки, європейської інтеграції та міжнародного співробітництва, Української Інженерно-Педагогічної Академії***ІНТЕГРАЦІЯ ШТУЧНОГО ІНТЕЛЕКТУ У ПРОЦЕС ВИВЧЕННЯ ІНОЗЕМНИХ МОВ У ЗВО:
ПЕРЕВАГИ, ВИКЛИКИ ТА МАЙБУТНІ НАПРЯМКИ****Abstract.**

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies into foreign language learning has revolutionized traditional methods, offering personalized, efficient, and enjoyable learning experiences. This paper explores the significant influence of AI on foreign language teaching at university, examining cutting-edge tools and approaches while addressing their advantages and limitations. AI-powered platforms, interactive apps, language assistants, and intelligent tutors are analyzed for their role in enhancing learning outcomes. Despite AI's benefits in accessibility, efficiency, and motivation, challenges such as cultural sensitivity, lack of human interaction, and adaptability persist. The importance of human interaction in language learning is emphasized, alongside the need for further research in adaptive systems, gamification, assessment, and ethical considerations. By navigating these complexities, educators and researchers can harness AI's potential to transform foreign language education in higher educational institutions. Furthermore, this paper delves into the ethical implications of using AI in foreign language teaching, such as data privacy and biases embedded within AI algorithms. It highlights the necessity for educators to strike a balance between the integration of AI technologies and the preservation of human connection in the language learning process. Through continued exploration and collaboration, we can pave the way for a future where AI enhances, rather than replaces, the intricacies of foreign language education.

Анотація.

Інтеграція технологій штучного інтелекту (ШІ) у вивчення іноземних мов дозволила революціонізувати традиційні методи, пропонуючи персоналізований, ефективний і приємний досвід навчання. У цій статті досліджується значний вплив штучного інтелекту на викладання іноземних мов в університетах, розглядаються найсучасніші інструменти та підходи, а також їхні переваги та недоліки. Платформи на основі штучного інтелекту, інтерактивні додатки, мовні асистенти та інтелектуальні репетитори аналізуються з точки зору їхньої ролі у покращенні результатів навчання. Попри переваги штучного інтелекту в доступності, ефективності та мотивації, залишаються такі проблеми, як культурна чутливість, брак інтерактивності та адаптивності. Підкреслюється важливість людської взаємодії у вивченні іноземної мови, а також необхідність подальших досліджень у галузі адаптивних систем, гейміфікації, оцінювання та етичних аспектів. Крім того, у цій статті розглядаються етичні наслідки використання ШІ у викладанні іноземних мов, такі як конфіденційність даних та упередженість, закладена в алгоритмах ШІ. Авторки підкреслюють необхідність для викладачів дотримуватися балансу між інтеграцією технологій штучного інтелекту та збереженням людського зв'язку у процесі вивчення мови. Враховуючи зазначені складнощі, викладачі та дослідники можуть використати потенціал штучного інтелекту для вдосконалення ініомовної освіти у вищих навчальних закладах. Продовжуючи дослідження та співпрацю, ми можемо прокласти шлях до майбутнього, в якому штучний інтелект доповнюватиме, а не замінюватиме тонкощі навчання іноземним мовам.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, foreign language learning, higher education, language learning platforms, adaptive learning systems, human interaction.

Ключові слова: Штучний Інтелект, вивчення іноземних мов, вища освіта, мовні навчальні платформи, адаптивні навчальні системи, людська взаємодія.

Formulation of the problem. The rapid and dynamic progress of science and technology has led to significant growth and continuous evolution of

knowledge, resulting in the constant aging and updating of information. This has led to profound transfor-

mations in the contemporary system of higher education, necessitating intensive adaptation and change. At the same time, technology is constantly advancing, enabling the efficient creation, storage, transmission, and perception of information. Learning a foreign language has perpetually represented a crucial skill for personal development, career advancement, and cultural appreciation. However, we now find traditional methods of language learning laborious and not always effective. With the rapid development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, the process of learning a foreign language is becoming increasingly accessible, efficient, and enjoyable. By exploring the impact of AI on foreign language learning at the university level, we can gain a deeper understanding of how these innovative tools can significantly enhance the overall learning experience for students. In addition, we can gain valuable insights into the potential limitations that arise from using AI in language education. This comprehensive analysis will benefit both educators and researchers in the field. The purpose of this paper is to examine the significant influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the learning of foreign languages in university environments. The goal is to thoroughly examine the latest cutting-edge tools and AI-driven approaches used in language learning, while also identifying the numerous advantages and limitations associated with integrating AI tools into the overall learning process.

Presentation of the main material. The constant development of the Internet and digital technologies expands the horizons of language learning. Online platforms, language exchanges and mobile apps make learning much easier, more convenient and accessible. But nowadays, artificial intelligence is giving a new dimension to language learning by providing a personalized and engaging experience. Previously, learning a new language usually required attending classes, using textbooks, and practicing with native speakers. While these methods can still yield results in today's world, they often demand a considerable investment of time, mental effort, and financial resources. However, AI-powered language learning platforms can provide personalized feedback, adaptive exercises, and immersive simulations to greatly enhance the learning experience. These advancements in technology have the potential to make language learning more efficient and enjoyable for learners of all levels [1].

Artificial intelligence-based tools for foreign language learning include:

Personalized learning platforms - use machine learning algorithms to tailor courses to each learner's proficiency level and needs. Artificial intelligence-based language learning apps are gaining popularity due to their capacity to adjust to the specific needs and preferences of each student. These apps utilize machine learning algorithms to analyze user progress and deliver personalized feedback and suggestions, enhancing the efficiency and engagement of the learning process.

Exploring the aims of the study, let's examine some AI-based platforms currently utilized in language teaching and learning: TalkPal: Affordable, high-performance language learning platform using AI. Duolingo: AI-powered app with personalized curriculum,

error analysis, engaging activities. Rosetta Stone: Advanced speech recognition, personalized feedback, wide range of languages. Babbel: AI-powered app for practical conversations, customizable content. Mondly: Revolutionary language learning app with AI-powered chatbots and voice recognition. Busuu: Wide variety of languages, interaction with native speakers, personalized lessons.

Interactive language learning apps provide a spirited and captivating method for acquiring new language skills, incorporating speech recognition and text analysis technologies to track progress and provide valuable suggestions. These apps offer personalized feedback and interactive exercises that make language learning a fun and engaging experience. Whether you are a novice or a proficient learner, these applications guarantee that you possess the essential resources to enhance your language proficiency with utmost efficiency. Interactive language learning apps offer a variety of exercises, games, and interactive tasks that make the learning process more enjoyable and efficient [2]. Here are some examples of such apps: Memrise: This app offers fun exercises and games to memorize words, phrases, and grammar in different languages. It also uses a repetition technique to reinforce memorization. Quizlet: This app allows you to create your own sets of cards to learn words and phrases in a foreign language. It also offers various games and quizzes to test your knowledge. HelloTalk: This app allows you to communicate with native speakers from all over the world through chat, voice messages and video calls. It helps students practice speaking and improve their communication skills. Rosetta Stone: Furthermore, as previously mentioned, Rosetta Stone provides interactive lessons and exercises for language learning, employing a methodology that simulates the natural acquisition of language. These apps help learners engage in language learning through playful and interactive methods that promote better memorization and mastery of the material.

Language assistants and chatbots offer real-time spoken language practice through the use of natural language and adaptive algorithms that adapt to the user's individual needs. They can offer pronunciation feedback based on the user's speech patterns and help them enhance their foreign language skills in a personalized manner. Additionally, these language assistants can also offer vocabulary and grammar exercises tailored to the user's proficiency level. Google Translate: Language translation tool with a learning feature. LUIS: Natural language chatbot for language learning. ChatGPT: GPT-based chatbot for practicing spoken language. Tandem: Language exchange app for practicing spoken language in real time.

Language assistants and chatbots offer learners the unique opportunity to practice a language in real time, receive instant feedback, and enhance their foreign language skills.

Intelligent Tutors harness the power of data analytics and learning algorithms to deliver personalized recommendations, tutorials, and exercises that are tailored to each student's unique learning style and historical success. This personalized approach enables stu-

dents to receive focused support and guidance, ultimately resulting in enhanced learning outcomes and heightened engagement in the learning process. It also enables educators to track students' progress and provide timely intervention when needed. Examples of language learning platforms that use intelligent tutoring and machine learning algorithms to tailor lessons to each student's proficiency level and needs include Lingvist, FluentU, Voxy, and Busuu. These platforms offer personalized recommendations, interactive exercises, and lessons based on real-life situations to enhance the language learning experience.

Intelligent tutors play a crucial role in enhancing foreign language learning, as they offer personalized lessons, valuable feedback, and tailored recommendations derived from meticulous data analysis of learners' progress [3].

All the AI tools mentioned share the same goal: to improve the experience of learning a foreign language by using advanced AI technologies. These tools strive to offer greater convenience, improved efficiency, and enhanced accessibility for learners.

Based on the analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature and our own practical experience of using AI technologies, we would like to outline the advantages of the above-mentioned technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language in the context of higher professional education:

Enhancing the efficiency of educational practices. The use of AI-based language learning tools can dramatically expedite the learning process by delivering immediate feedback, pinpointing areas for improvement, and adapting learning materials accordingly. This allows learners to focus on their weaknesses and make rapid progress.

Mastering pronunciation and perfecting your accent. One of the most challenging aspects of language learning is mastering pronunciation and accent. AI-based tools can provide real-time feedback on pronunciation, allowing learners to correct their mistakes and develop a more authentic accent.

Improved accessibility. AI has made language learning more accessible to people who may not have access to traditional learning resources. Thanks to AI-powered apps and platforms, anyone with a smartphone or internet connection can learn a new language from anywhere in the world.

Increasing student motivation and engagement in the academic process. AI-based language learning tools often include elements of gamification and personalized feedback that can help keep students motivated and engaged. This is critical to maintaining long-term engagement in the foreign language learning process.

Artificial Intelligence is undeniably a powerful tool for teaching foreign languages. However, the implementation of this technology in the classroom presents certain challenges and limitations that need to be addressed:

The lack of context and cultural sensitivity in AI can lead to a limited understanding of cultural aspects and context. This can make accurate translation and interpretation of expressions and idioms difficult.

Translators and interpreters face a significant challenge when it comes to accurately translating expressions, idioms, and metaphors that are heavily influenced by context and cultural subtleties. AI interpreters may struggle with capturing the full meaning and essence of such linguistic nuances. This can lead to misunderstandings or mistranslations in certain situations. For example: contextual understanding. Some AI systems may have a limited grasp of the context in which a particular word or expression is used. This can lead to misinterpretation of messages or misinterpretation of meaning in translation.

Cultural norms and customs pose a challenge for AI in accurately interpreting and using language. AI may struggle to incorporate the nuances of cultural practices and values that influence language usage. For instance, there could be variations in how polite requests are formulated or how respect for the interlocutor is conveyed across different cultures [4].

Semantic nuances. Language use can be saturated with semantic nuances that can be difficult for AI to pick up on. For instance, a single word can hold varying meanings depending on its context or intonation, causing challenges in accurate translation or interpretation. In English, the word "freedom" can have different shades of meaning depending on the context. For instance, the concept of "freedom of speech" encompasses more than just the right to express oneself—it also entails the absence of any form of censorship or governmental restrictions.

Constraints in material diversity. Certain AI education platforms might face limitations in terms of available resources or instructional approaches, creating challenges in catering to individual student needs and learning preferences.

Speech recognition accuracy issues. Speech recognition systems can sometimes misinterpret pronunciation or have limitations in recognizing accents or dialects.

One disadvantage of using AI for language learning is the absence of human interaction. Although AI offers automated learning methods, it fails to provide learners with the valuable experience of interacting with real people. This lack of human feedback can significantly hinder the effectiveness of language acquisition. The lack of human interaction can be significant for several reasons: inability to ask questions and seek clarification: Unlike a real teacher or tutor, artificial intelligence may have limitations in its ability to engage in open-ended conversations and provide personalized explanations. This can create difficulties if a learner wants to seek further clarification or ask questions about a particular topic [5,6]. Despite the advantages that artificial intelligence offers in language learning, the absence of human interaction can present challenges for certain students, particularly when they require personalized support and interpersonal communication.

Lack of immediate feedback. Human interaction facilitates immediate feedback on one's mistakes and progress. However, when it comes to artificial intelligence, feedback is often limited to predefined algorithms, which pose challenges in correcting errors and

sharpening skills. Some learners find it important to be able to socialize and interact with others during the learning process, as it helps enhance their overall experience. The absence of interpersonal interaction in artificial intelligence-led learning can result in feelings of isolation or a lack of motivation.

Adapting to individual needs. A human teacher can more flexibly adjust to the specific needs of each student, offering a personalized approach to learning. Artificial intelligence may be limited to standardized algorithms, which may not always meet the unique needs of each student.

Difficulty managing multilingualism. Some AI systems may struggle to process and adapt to multilingual environments, leading to a lack of opportunities for learners who are trying to learn multiple languages at the same time.

Conclusions and perspectives of further research. Although AI greatly improves the accessibility and efficiency of language learning, it is crucial to remain vigilant about its challenges and limitations. Being aware of its use and its boundaries is essential. Despite the numerous benefits of AI-based language learning, it is crucial not to overlook the significance of human interaction in the learning process. Interacting with native speakers, engaging in conversations, and immersing oneself in the culture of the target language offer unique and invaluable learning opportunities that AI is unable to fully replicate. Furthermore, participating in human interaction offers learners the chance to actively develop and improve their listening and speaking skills in real time. It enables them to receive prompt feedback and correction from proficient speakers, fostering rapid progress. The interactive component of foreign language learning is crucial for developing fluency and natural communication skills that go beyond mere translation and vocabulary acquisition.

Research in AI technologies for foreign language learning is a dynamic and fast-evolving field, offering numerous opportunities for further exploration. These

encompass adaptive learning systems, gamification, immersive learning environments, as well as assessment and evaluation, along with ethical and pedagogical considerations. By exploring these and other avenues of research, scholars and practitioners can continually push the boundaries of AI technologies for foreign language learning in higher education. This will ultimately enhance the accessibility, effectiveness, and engagement of language learning for students worldwide.

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